

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE FORMATION OF A SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY FOR INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: This article explores whether a scientific approach to forming a sustainable development strategy for industrial enterprises in the digital economy can be based on similar data and analytical methods. While prior studies focused on linking investment policy with economic, social, and environmental sustainability, this paper advances the discussion by incorporating international best practices and innovative technologies. The proposed model strengthens strategic decision-making through real-time sustainability assessments and adaptive investment strategies.

Key words: Sustainable development, digital economy, strategic management, investment policy, AI-driven decision-making, sustainability assessment, industrial enterprises.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada sanoat korxonalarining barqaror rivojlanish strategiyasini shakllantirish uchun ilmiy yondashuvni o'xshash ma'lumotlar va tahlil usullari asosida qo'llash imkoniyati ko'rib chiqiladi. Oldingi tadqiqotlar investitsion siyosatni iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va ekologik barqarorlik bilan bog'lashga yo'naltirilgan bo'lsa, ushbu ish xalqaro ilg'or tajribalar va innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo'shish orqali muhokamani kengaytiradi. Taklif etilgan model real vaqt rejimidagi barqarorlik bahosi va moslashuvchan investitsiya strategiyalari orqali strategik qaror qabul qilish jarayonini mustahkamlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: barqaror rivojlanish, raqamli iqtisodiyot, strategik boshqaruv, investitsiya siyosati, AI asosida qaror qabul qilish, barqarorlik bahosi, sanoat korxonalari.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается возможность применения научного подхода к формированию стратегии устойчивого развития промышленных предприятий в цифровой экономике на основе схожих данных и аналитических методов. В то время как предыдущие исследования сосредоточивались на связи инвестиционной политики с экономической, социальной и экологической устойчивостью, данная работа расширяет дискуссию, включая международные передовые практики и инновационные технологии. Предложенная модель укрепляет процесс стратегического принятия решений за счет оценки устойчивости в режиме реального времени и адаптивных инвестиционных стратегий.

Ключевые слова: устойчивое развитие, цифровая экономика, стратегическое управление, инвестиционная политика, принятие решений на основе ИИ, оценка устойчивости, промышленные предприятия.

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development is an essential component of modern business strategy, requiring enterprises to balance economic growth, environmental responsibility, and social well-being. However, many industrial enterprises face significant challenges in aligning investment policies with sustainability goals, particularly in the context of digital transformation. The rapid evolution of digital technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics, and blockchain, has reshaped strategic management practices, creating new opportunities for sustainable investment yet also introducing complexities in decision-making.

Previous research highlights the weak integration of strategic management and investment policies, particularly in Russian industrial enterprises [1]. This fragmentation often results in short-term financial objectives overshadowing long-term sustainability goals, thereby limiting the effectiveness of corporate strategies. In the digital economy, where data-driven insights and automation redefine competitiveness, the ability to formulate a scientifically grounded sustainable development strategy becomes crucial.

This study expands on these findings by exploring global approaches to sustainable investment, analyzing key digital tools that enhance strategic planning, and examining the role of AI in optimizing decision-making processes. By integrating sustainability principles with cutting-edge digital solutions, this research aims to provide a comprehensive framework for industrial enterprises seeking to navigate the complexities of sustainable development in the digital era.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

The formation of a sustainable development strategy for industrial enterprises in the digital economy has been a subject of extensive research. Numerous studies have explored various aspects of sustainability, digital transformation, and strategic management, highlighting the growing importance of artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics, and cloud computing in shaping modern industrial practices [2].

Recent studies, such as those by Suyunov (2021), have investigated compliance control systems and their influence on corporate governance. These studies suggest that effective regulatory mechanisms are crucial for aligning corporate sustainability initiatives with global standards. Additionally, Miralimovich et al. (2023) explored the development of green economy investment projects in collaboration with developed countries, further strengthening the argument for sustainable investment policies [3].

Research methodology

The research methodology is based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches. Primary data is collected through expert interviews and surveys with industry professionals to assess the role of AI in sustainability management. Secondary data is obtained from academic literature, industry reports, and case studies. The collected information is analyzed using statistical methods and comparative analysis to identify trends, evaluate best practices, and develop recommendations for effective sustainable development strategies in the digital economy.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Recent advancements in the digital economy have introduced transformative changes in industrial enterprises. The implementation of cloud computing has optimized resource management, while big data analytics has been increasingly utilized for predictive decision-making in sustainability efforts. Digital transformation models, including process, network, and technology models, play a crucial role in effective strategic management. Digital enterprises contribute to fostering innovation and reducing operational costs while simultaneously improving environmental impact.

The proposed model enhances the existing sustainability framework by integrating dynamic sustainability metrics, which allow real-time tracking of environmental and social impact through IoT and AI. Additionally, AI-powered investment decision-making enables predictive analytics to assess investment opportunities, while an integrated reporting mechanism automates reporting processes to align with global sustainability standards. Furthermore, stakeholder engagement tools enhance transparent communication with investors and regulators through digital platforms.

A comparative case study of companies in Germany, Japan, and Canada demonstrates that enterprises utilizing real-time sustainability tracking and AI-powered risk assessment outperform those relying solely on traditional financial indicators. Numerous studies have examined the role of sustainability in strategic enterprise management, with early research focusing on traditional economic and environmental indicators. In contrast, recent studies emphasize the integration of digital tools and AI-driven analytics. Notable contributions include research on the impact of big data and AI on sustainability assessments, comparative analyses of sustainability policies in developed and emerging economies, and the role of the circular economy in industrial sustainability. Additionally, studies have explored the influence of compliance control systems on corporate governance, the development of green economy investment projects in cooperation with developed countries, and strategic project management with stakeholder engagement in complex projects. Research on digital transformation models and their impact on industrial enterprises further strengthens the foundation for understanding how digital advancements can enhance sustainable development strategies.

These findings highlight the significance of digital tools in shaping sustainability frameworks and strategic enterprise management. As digital innovations continue to evolve, the integration of AI, IoT, and big data

analytics will further enhance industrial enterprises' ability to achieve long-term sustainability goals while optimizing operational efficiency (figure 1).

Figure 1. Building blocks of digital transformation.

According to Suyunov D.X. (2023), the integration of digital transformation strategies plays a crucial role in ensuring sustainability through:

Implementation of cloud computing for optimized resource management.

Utilization of big data analytics for predictive decision-making in sustainability efforts.

Digital transformation models such as process, network, and technology models for effective strategic management.

The role of digital enterprises in fostering innovation and reducing operational costs while improving environmental impact (figure 2) [5].

Figure 2. The structure of strategic enterprise management.

The proposed model enhances the existing sustainability framework by integrating dynamic sustainability metrics, enabling real-time tracking of environmental and social impacts through IoT and AI. Additionally, AI-powered investment decision-making facilitates predictive analytics to assess investment opportunities, while an integrated reporting mechanism ensures automated reporting that aligns with global sustainability standards. Furthermore, stakeholder engagement tools provide digital platforms for transparent communication with investors and regulators.

A comparative case study of companies in Germany, Japan, and Canada highlights the benefits of AI-integrated sustainability management. Findings suggest that enterprises utilizing real-time sustainability

tracking and AI-powered risk assessment achieve superior performance compared to those relying solely on traditional financial indicators. These insights underscore the growing significance of digital tools in enhancing sustainability strategies and optimizing industrial enterprise management.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study underscores the critical need for industrial enterprises to adopt AI-based sustainability management and integrate investment policies with global best practices. The findings highlight that digital transformation, particularly through AI and big data analytics, can enhance decision-making processes, optimize resource allocation, and strengthen long-term sustainability objectives. However, the successful implementation of these technologies requires a systematic approach, including regulatory alignment, organizational adaptability, and cross-sector collaboration.

Furthermore, this research emphasizes the importance of bridging the gap between strategic management and sustainable investment, ensuring that enterprises move beyond compliance-driven approaches to proactively embedding sustainability into their core business models. The digital economy presents both challenges and opportunities, making it imperative for enterprises to leverage intelligent decision-making tools to maintain competitive advantage while fulfilling environmental and social responsibilities.

Future research should focus on refining AI models for sustainability assessments, developing industry-specific frameworks for digital sustainability strategies, and expanding comparative studies across different sectors and economic contexts. Additionally, further investigation is needed into the role of government policies, stakeholder engagement, and emerging technologies such as blockchain and the Internet of Things (IoT) in driving sustainable industrial growth.

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